

e-ISSN: 3048-4766

Room Air Quality Indicator

**Volume 08 Issue 01 Jan-
Apr 2026**

**Noorain P^{1*}, Priya K², Sanjeev Kumar R A³,
Megha Upase⁴**

***Corresponding Author:**
Noorain P,
*Student, Department of
Electrical and Electronics
Engineering, P D A College
of Engineering, Kalaburagi,
Karnataka, India*

^{1,2}*Student, Department of Electrical and Electronics
Engineering, P D A College of Engineering, Kalaburagi,
Karnataka, India*

^{3,4}*Professor, Department of Electrical and Electronics
Engineering, P D A College of Engineering, Kalaburagi,
Karnataka, India*

Submission Date: Dec 18,
2025

Copyright Received Date:
Dec 23, 2025

ABSTRACT

Air is important things that people need to live, yet the quality of air indoors is often ignored. Most people their time inside rooms, such as in homes, schools, and offices. If the air inside these places is not clean, it can affect our health, mood, and ability to concentrate. Poor indoor air quality can cause problems like headaches, dizziness, coughing, and even long-term breathing issues. Common reasons for bad air inside a room include a lack of ventilation, dust, smoke, high carbon dioxide (CO₂) levels, and harmful gases released from paints, furniture, or cleaning materials. Because of this, it is necessary to have a simple and affordable way to check how clean or polluted the air is in a room. This project, titled "Room Air Quality Indicator," is designed to measure and show the quality of air inside a room in real time. The main goal is to build a system that can sense different air parameters and alert people when the air quality becomes poor. The system uses various sensors to detect carbon dioxide levels, temperature, humidity, and the presence of dust or other particles in the air. These sensors send data to a small controller, such as an Arduino or ESP32, which processes the readings. The processed data is then displayed through LEDs or a digital screen, showing whether the air is in a "Good," "Moderate," or "Poor" condition. Let us consider, a green light may indicate clean air, yellow may show moderate quality, and red may warn that the air is unhealthy.

This project provides a practical solution for monitoring and maintaining indoor air quality. It combines the use of basic electronic components and sensors to create an efficient, affordable, and user-friendly device. By

developing and using this system, individuals can better understand the quality of the air they breathe every day and take the necessary steps to make their surroundings safer and more comfortable. The Room Air Quality Indicator not only promotes health awareness but also how technology can be used in simple ways to solve real-life problems related to the environment and human health.

Keywords:- *Indoor Air Quality (IAQ), Air Quality Monitoring, Arduino UNO, Gas Sensor (MQ135), Real-Time Monitoring*

INTRODUCTION

Air is definitely the most essential parts of our environment and directly affects our health and well-being. While people are concerned about outdoor air pollution caused by vehicles and factories, indoor air pollution is often overlooked. The air inside homes, classrooms, and offices can sometimes be even more polluted than the air outside. This happens because closed rooms often have poor ventilation, allowing harmful substances such as carbon dioxide (CO₂), dust, smoke, and volatile organic compounds (VOCs) from paints, furniture, or cleaning materials to build up over time.

Breathing in such polluted air can lead to health problems like headaches, allergies, asthma, tiredness, and difficulty focusing. In recently years, indoor air quality monitoring has become an important topic around the world. With people spending nearly 80–90% of their time indoors, there is a growing awareness about how indoor air affects daily life, productivity, and long-term health. Many modern buildings and smart homes now include air quality monitoring systems to keep track of CO₂ levels, humidity, and temperature.

These systems use advanced sensors and IoT technologies to get the data and sometimes even control ventilation systems automatically. However, most commercial devices that monitor indoor air quality are expensive and not easily available for everyone, especially students, small offices, and families who just want a simple way to check their air quality.

This is where the Room Air Quality Indicator project comes in. The main goal of this project is to create a low-cost and easy-to-use device that can check the quality of air inside a room in real time. The system uses a set of sensors to measure important air parameters such as carbon dioxide (CO₂), temperature, humidity, and the level of dust or small particles in the air.

The data from these sensors is sent to a microcontroller, like an Arduino or ESP32, which processes the readings and shows the results through colored LED indicators or a small display. For example, a green light means good air, yellow means fair, and red means poor air quality. This makes it simple for anyone to understand the air quality at a glance.

Indoor air quality is a major health concern. This paper reviews many recent systems that use Internet of Things (IoT) technologies to monitor IAQ. It looks at what sensors are used, how these systems are built (architecture, connectivity), and what the main challenges are. It serves as a good overview of how IAQ monitoring has developed in recent years. [1]

This study uses low-cost sensors to monitor indoor air quality in dormitories/residences at a university. Because students spend a lot of time indoors, the authors argue continuous IAQ monitoring is important. They show that affordable sensor networks can detect pollutant levels and help improve living environments for students. [2]

This paper describes the design of a smart system to monitor indoor air quality in real time using sensors and a microcontroller (Arduino Uno). They tested the system in different parts of a home/residential environment and found it can reliably monitor air quality indicators. It shows a project approach to IAQ monitoring. [3]

The authors use inexpensive sensors to track fine particulate matter (PM_{2.5}) and CO₂ in homes. They found that cooking increases PM_{2.5} dramatically; CO₂ increases during sleeping hours. They perform a health-risk assessment and show how low-cost sensors can give useful data on indoor air quality. [4]

METHODOLOGY AND WORKING:

The project focuses on developing an air quality monitoring system using two different approaches: a pure hardware-based setup and an IoT-based system. In the hardware-based approach, the system is designed using essential electronic components to monitor air quality

directly through physical devices. Sensors such as MQ-135 (for detecting harmful gases like CO₂, NH₃, and other pollutants), DHT11 or DHT22 (for measuring temperature and humidity), and a dust or PM_{2.5} sensor are connected to a microcontroller such as Arduino or STM32.

The microcontroller continuously collects and goes through data from these sensors in real time. The readings are displayed on an LCD or LED screen so users can instantly see the air quality conditions. Preset threshold levels are programmed into the system if any value exceeds a safe limit, the system triggers visual or audio alerts through multi-color LEDs (e.g., green for good, yellow for moderate, and red for poor air quality) or a buzzer. This approach ensures the system operates independently without requiring an internet connection. In the IoT-based approach, the same sensor setup is integrated with wireless communication modules such as Wi-Fi or ZigBee to enable real-time data transmission.

The collected data is sent to an online cloud platform or local server, where it is stored, analyzed, and displayed through a user-friendly web or mobile dashboard. Users can monitor air quality trends remotely and receive notifications when pollutant levels rise above acceptable limits. This approach enables continuous monitoring, data logging, and easy access to historical information. Finally, both systems are tested in different indoor environments such as rooms, offices, and classrooms to compare their performance, accuracy, and reliability. The results help evaluate the effectiveness of each method and demonstrate how IoT integration can enhance traditional hardware-based air quality monitoring systems.

BLOCK DIAGRAM

Fig.1:-Block Diagram

- The **Power Supply** block provides the necessary electrical energy for the system's operation. It can be obtained from a DC adapter, USB connection, or battery, typically supplying 5V or 9V depending on the components used. This block ensures that stable and consistent power is available for the sensor, microcontroller, and display to function properly.
- The **Air Quality Sensor**, such as the MQ135, detects various gases and pollutants present inside the room. It senses harmful gases like carbon dioxide, ammonia, nitrogen oxides, and smoke, and converts the concentration of these gases into an electrical signal. The output voltage of the sensor changes according to the level of air contamination clean air produces a low voltage signal, while polluted air produces a higher voltage.
- The **Microcontroller**, often an Arduino Uno or similar device, acts as the brain of the system. It receives the analog signal from the sensor, processes it, and determines the corresponding air quality level. Based on the data, the microcontroller decides what message to display and which indicators to activate. It essentially interprets sensor data and converts it into meaningful information for the user.
- The **Display Unit** shows the air quality status in real-time. It can be a simple LCD or OLED screen that presents readings such as "Good," "Moderate," or "Poor," or numerical values like the Air Quality Index (AQI) or gas concentration in parts per million (ppm). This allows users to easily monitor the condition of the air around them.

- Finally, the **Indicator Block** provides immediate visual or audible feedback. LEDs of different colors typically green, yellow, and red are used to show air quality levels at a glance, while a buzzer can sound an alert when

the air becomes hazardous. Together, the display and indicator units ensure the user is promptly informed about the state of their indoor air, promoting a healthier and safer living environment.

CIRCUIT DIAGRAM:

Fig.2:-Circuit Diagram

- This diagram represents a microcontroller-based air quality monitoring system designed to detect harmful gases and display the results. At the core of the system is the Arduino UNO, which functions as the main processing unit. It continuously receives data from the air quality sensor, analyzes the signal, and controls the output display. The Arduino is powered through a regulated 5V breadboard power supply module, which distributes a stable voltage to all connected components via the breadboard power rails.
- The air quality sensor module, placed on the left side of the diagram, is responsible for sensing the presence of polluted gases in the surrounding air. This sensor converts gas

concentration into an electrical signal. Because the sensor uses surface-mount pins, an SMD-to-DIP adapter board is used for the connections making it compatible with the breadboard. The sensor's VCC and GND pins are wired to the power rails, while its signal (TXD/output) line is linked to the Arduino input pin, allowing the controller to read pollution levels accurately.

- The breadboard serves as an interconnection platform, enabling easy wiring between the Arduino, sensor, power supply, and display without permanent soldering. The 16x2 LCD display is connected to the Arduino through control and data pins are used to present real-time air quality information. It displays readable messages or values that

indicate the condition of the air, such as normal or polluted levels. Together, these components form a compact and low-cost system that continuously monitors indoor air

quality and provides clear visual feedback, helping users understand and respond to changes in their environment.

RESULTS

The AQ Monitoring System successfully measured the surrounding temperature, humidity, and gas levels using the DHT11 and MQ135 sensors. The processed values were displayed clearly on the 16x2 LCD, allowing easy observation of environmental conditions.

The LED indicators responded accurately to changes in air quality, shifting from green to yellow or red based on pollution levels. During testing, the buzzer activated whenever gas concentration crossed the preset threshold, effectively warning about unsafe air conditions. Overall, the system performed reliably and provided consistent readings suitable for basic environmental monitoring.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the Air Quality Monitoring System proved to be a simple yet solution for tracking basic environmental parameters. By integrating low-cost sensors with the Arduino UNO, the system was able to detect poor air quality and alert users through visual and audio indicators.

Although not as precise as industrial-grade equipment, it provides a practical and affordable method for understanding and responding to changes in air pollution. This project demonstrates how microcontroller-based systems can contribute to environmental awareness and help users maintain a safer, healthier living space.

REFERENCES

1. Sai, J., Dutta, M., & Marques, G. (2020). *Indoor air quality monitoring systems based on Internet of Things: A systematic review*.
2. Afroz, R., Guo, X., Cheng, C., Delorme, A., Duruisseau-Kuntz, R., & Zhao, R. (2023). *Investigating indoor air quality in university residences using low-cost sensors*.
3. Rudavskiy, I., Klym, H., & Popov, A. (2023). *Design and evaluation of a smart indoor air quality monitoring system*.
4. Shah, K. B., Kim, D., Pinakana, S. D., Hobosyan, M., Montes, A., & Raysoni, A. U. (2024). *Evaluating indoor air quality in residential environments: A study of PM_{2.5} and CO₂ dynamics using low-cost sensors*.
5. Acharya, K., & Kolekar, S. V. (2024). *Air quality monitoring system development using IoT for indoor applications*.
6. Berkani, M. R. A., Chouchane, A., Himeur, Y., Ouamane, A., & Amira, A. (2023). *An intelligent edge-deployable indoor air quality monitoring and activity recognition approach*.
7. Alhmiedat, T., & Samara, G. (2017). *A low cost ZigBee sensor network architecture for indoor air quality monitoring*.
8. Irbah, N., Nurika, G., & Ramani, A. (2024). *Implementation of indoor air quality monitoring systems of particulate matter 2.5 based on the Internet of Things*.